

2-Hydroxy-4-Methylacetophenone Oxime (HMAOX) as an Analytical Reagent : Part III. Studies on Nickel Chelate

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2-Hydroxy-4-methyl acetophenone oxime¹ (HMAOX) has been used as a reagent for gravimetric estimation of nickel and for its separation from other ions. The precipitation of the metal by the reagent is complete between pH 5.0 to 10.0 and after drying at 120°, the composition of the precipitate corresponds to the formula Ni(C₉H₁₀O₂N)₂. It is also observed that by proper control of pH or by using masking agents it is possible to estimate nickel in presence of several cations. The reagent has also been used in the separation and determination of nickel in its binary mixtures with copper.

THE well-known reagents for gravimetric determination of nickel in presence of other ions are dimethylglyoxime², nioxime³, 2-hydroxy-5-methyl propiophenone oxime⁴ etc. The purpose of the present investigation is to use new ligand HMAOX¹ for the gravimetric determination of nickel. HMAOX gives a green precipitate which nickel between pH range 5.0 to 10.0. Interference due to several ions has been removed by controlling the pH or by using suitable masking agents.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. Grade. Stock solution of nickel was prepared by dissolving NiSO₄·7H₂O in double distilled water and standardized gravimetrically. Solutions of other ions were prepared from samples of corresponding salts. An ethanolic solution of the ligand was employed and the pH was adjusted using acetic acid and ammonium hydroxide buffer.

Synthesis of the reagent :

2-Hydroxy-4-methyl acetophenone⁵ was obtained in almost quantitative yield by Fries migration of *m*-cresyl acetate⁶ in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

Its oxime⁵ was prepared by the reaction of the above ketone with hydroxyl amine hydrochloride and potassium hydroxide (40%) in dilute ethanol. It was crystallised from petroleum, m.p. 102°.

Determination of nickel :

A known volume of nickel solution taken in a beaker was diluted to about 100 ml. and the necessary

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pH was adjusted using an acetic acid and ammonium hydroxide buffer. The solution was warmed to 60°-70° and a calculated volume of ethanolic solution of the reagent was added with constant stirring until no more precipitation took place on adding excess of reagent solution. The precipitate was digested on a water-bath for 30 min. It was filtered while hot, through a sintered glass crucible (G.4) and washed with hot water (60°-70°) to remove foreign ions and the buffer adhering to the precipitate. The precipitate was finally washed with 60 percent ethanol. The precipitate was dried at 120° to constant weight. It has been found that nickel can be quantitatively determined in the pH range 5.0 to 10.0. The conversion factor (nickel/nickel complex) is 0.1518. Results of some of the estimations are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL

(pH of the solution, 5.5)

Nickel taken mg.	Nickel complex obtained mg.	Nickel found mg.	Error in mg.
3.0	18.9	2.9	-0.1
6.0	41.0	6.2	+0.2
17.8	118.0	17.9	+0.1
20.9	139.0	21.1	+0.2
29.8	196.0	29.7	-0.1
59.4	393.0	59.7	+0.3

Effect of foreign ions on precipitation of nickel :

Wherever possible, the interfering ions have been masked with suitable masking agent or sequestered by sequestering agent, e.g., Ti⁴⁺ has been masked by adding potassium fluoride, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺ and V⁵⁺ have been sequestered by adding sodium potassium tartrate. In some cases the interference has been

removed by changing the pH of mixed solution, e.g., several cations like Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Co²⁺ (at pH 5.5); Cd²⁺ (at pH 6.0), Ag⁺ and Hg²⁺ (at pH 7.0) and sufficiently large excess of anions like PO₄³⁻, F⁻, SO₄²⁻ and Cl⁻ (at pH 5.5) could be tolerated in the determination of nickel at pH values given in brackets. Cu²⁺ and Pd²⁺ interfere as they are also precipitated by the reagent and should therefore be previously removed.

Separation and determination of copper and nickel :

When copper and nickel were present in the same solution copper¹ was precipitated first at pH 2.5 with HMAOX and determined gravimetrically. The filtrate was evaporated to about 100 ml; pH of the filtrate containing nickel was adjusted to 5.5 and was estimated with HMAOX as above. Some of the results given in Table 2 show that both copper and nickel can be accurately determined when present in the same solution.

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF CU AND NI

Metal taken mg.		Complex obtained mg.		Metal found mg.		Error in mg.	
Cu	Ni	Cu	Ni	Cu	Ni	Cu	Ni
16.2	20.9	101.0	138.0	16.4	21.0	+0.2	+0.1
24.4	29.8	151.0	198.0	24.5	30.1	+0.1	+0.3
31.4	59.4	194.0	390.0	31.5	59.2	+0.1	-0.2

Structure of complex :

The nickel complex was analysed for its carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content to determine its composition. The metal content was determined by standard analytical method [Found : C, 55.79;

H, 5.01; N, 7.11; Ni, 14.54; Calc. : C, 55.86; H, 5.17; N, 7.24; Ni, 15.18%]. The composition of the complex corresponds to the formula Ni(C₉H₁₀O₂N)₂ in which nickel to ligand ratio is 1 : 2. The mol. wt. determined cryoscopically using camphor as the solvent, showed the chelate to be monomeric i.e., the chelate could be represented by ML₂. The 1 : 2 stoichiometry is confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation. For this, the chelate was extracted in chloroform and the optical density of solution of metal content was determined. The maximum was found to be at 33% of M/M+L giving 1 : 2 composition of the chelate.

The nickel chelate is extractable in most of the non-polar organic solvents e.g., benzene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. This shows that in all probability the complex is neutral. Magnetic susceptibility measurements on the complex showed that it is diamagnetic in character.

On the basis of above results the structure(I) is assigned to the nickel complex.

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